

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

ON THE SPECTRUM OF A SECOND ORDER LINEAR INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL OPERATOR ON THE SEMI-AIS

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Abstract

We prove that subject to the conditions $\int_a^\infty |P(x)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, x, \rho)| ds \right] dx < B < \infty$ the eigen-values of the integro-differential (i.e.) operator L_θ form a bounded finite or denumerable set whose limit points can be located only on the positive semi-axis.

It is shown that subject to the conditions of the form

$$|P(x)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, x, \rho)| ds \right] < ce^{-2\varepsilon_0 x}, \varepsilon_0 > 0$$

the number of eigen-values of L_θ form a finite set.

In the paper it is shown the boundary of the domain in the complex λ plane ($\sqrt{\lambda} = \rho_1 + \omega_1 \rho_2$), outside which knowingly there is no spectrum of the integro-differential operator L_θ . And it is also proved that if λ belongs to the spectrum, then the resolvent of the integro-differential operator L_θ is a bounded integral operator with the kernel $T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho)$, satisfying the conditions

$$\int_0^\infty |T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho)|^2 dx < \infty, \int_0^\infty |T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho)|^2 d\tau < \infty.$$

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Introduction

Let us consider in $L^2(R^+)$ where R^+ is a semi-axis $(0, \infty)$ second order integro-differential equation

$$y''(x) + \lambda y(x) = p(x)y'(x) + \int_0^\infty k(x, s, \rho)y'(s, \rho)ds \quad (2.1)$$

and boundary condition

$$y'(0) - \theta y(0) = 0 \quad (2.2)$$

where θ is a fixed complex number, $\sqrt{\lambda} = \rho, \text{Im } \rho > 0$.

Let $p(x)$ be a complex valued summable function in the interval R^+ and the kernel of the integro-differential equation (2.1) have the form:

$$k(x, s, \rho) = \begin{cases} e^{-\rho\omega_1(s-x)} P(s)k^*(x, s, \rho) & \text{for } s < x, \\ e^{-\rho\omega_2(s-x)} P(s)k^*(x, s, \rho) & \text{for } s > x, \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

where ω_1, ω_2 are various roots of second degree from -1, while $k^*(x, s, \rho)$ is a complex-valued continuous bounded function on totality of variables (x, s, ρ) , $0 \leq x, s < \infty, \text{Im } \rho > 0$, and analytic with respect to ρ in the domain $(x, s), 0 \leq x, s < \infty$.

Let the following condition be fulfilled

$$\int_a^{\infty} |P(x)| \left[1 + \int_0^{\infty} |k^*(s, x, \rho)| ds \right] dx < B < \infty, \quad (2.4)$$

where B is independent of ρ .

Denote by L_{θ} on operator generated by the integro-differential expression

$$l(y) = -y''(x) + p(x)y'(x) + \int_0^{\infty} k(x, s, \rho)y'(s)ds$$

and the boundary condition (2.2) in Hilbert space $L^2(R^+)$.

The domain of definition $D(L_{\theta})$ of the integro-differential operator L_{θ} consists of the function $y(x)$, having the derivative $y'(x)$, absolutely continuous in each finite interval $(\alpha, \beta) \subset R^+$, satisfying the boundary condition (2.2) and such that $y(x) \in L^2(R^+)$ and $l(y) \in L^2(R^+)$. If $y(x) \in D(L_{\theta})$, then by the definition $L_{\theta}y = l(y)$.

Let us clarify the character of the integro-differential operator L_{θ} on a positive semi-axis. The general so-

lution of the integro-differential equation (2.1) has the form: $y(x, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^2 c_i u_i(x, \rho)$

where $u_1(x, \rho), u_2(x, \rho)$ are fundamental solutions of the inegro-differential equation (2.1).

As $u_1(x, \rho), u_2(x, \rho)$ we choose $y_1(x, \rho), y_2(x, \rho)$ constructed in the previous work. For them we have

$$y_1(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[1 + \frac{O(1)}{\rho\omega_1} \right], \quad y_1'(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} [\rho\omega_1 + O(1)]$$

and

$$y_2'(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_2 x} [\rho\omega_2 + O(1)].$$

Show that for $\rho > 0$ for any $c_1 \neq 0$, and $c_1 \neq 0$, $y(x) \in \bar{L}^2(R^+)$.

Indeed, let $|c_1| \neq |c_2|$ and $|c_1| > |c_2|$. Then for rather large x ,

$$\begin{aligned} |y|^2 &= \left| c_1 e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[1 + \frac{O(1)}{\rho\omega_1} \right] + c_2 e^{\rho\omega_2 x} \left[1 + \frac{O(1)}{\rho\omega_2} \right] \right|^2 = \\ &= |c_1|^2 + |c_2|^2 + 2 \operatorname{Re} |c_1 c_2| + \frac{O(1)}{\rho\omega_1} + \frac{O(1)}{\rho\omega_2} \geq \\ &\geq 2|c_1|^2 - 2|c_1||c_2| > 0. \end{aligned}$$

i.e. $y(x) \in \bar{L}^2(R^+)$.

In a similar way, $y(x) \in \bar{L}^2(R^+)$ for $|c_1| \neq |c_2|, |c_1| < |c_2|$.

Therefore, we can assume $|c_1| = |c_2| = 1$.

Let $c_1 = e^{\omega_1 \alpha_1}, c_2 = e^{\omega_2 \alpha_2}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 |y|^2 &= \left| e^{\omega_1 \alpha_1} e^{\rho \omega_1 x} + e^{\omega_2 \alpha_2} e^{\omega_2 x} \right|^2 + \frac{O(1)}{\omega_1 \rho} + \frac{O(1)}{\omega_2 \rho} = \\
 &= \left| e^{\omega_1 \frac{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2}{2}} \left| e^{\omega_1 \left(\rho x + \frac{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2}{2} \right)} + e^{\omega_2 \left(\rho x + \frac{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2}{2} \right)} \right|^2 + \frac{O(1)}{\omega_1 \rho} + \frac{O(1)}{\omega_2 \rho} = \right. \\
 &= \left| e^{\omega_1 (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)} \left| e^{\omega_1 \left(\rho x + \frac{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2}{2} \right)} + e^{\omega_2 \left(\rho x + \frac{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2}{2} \right)} \right|^2 + \frac{O(1)}{\rho \omega_1} + \frac{O(1)}{\rho \omega_2} = \right. \\
 &4 \cos^2 \left(\rho x + \frac{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2}{2} \right) + \frac{O(1)}{\rho \omega_1} + \frac{O(1)}{\rho \omega_2}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Let Δ_k be the intervals on the axis x , determined by the inequalities

$$-\frac{\pi}{4} + k\pi \leq \rho x + \frac{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2}{2} \leq \frac{\pi}{4} + k\pi.$$

In the Δ_k interval $\cos^2 \left(\rho x + \frac{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2}{2} \right) \geq \frac{1}{2}$, on the other hand, for any k and rather large we have:

$$\left| \frac{O(1)}{\rho_1 \omega_1} + \frac{O(1)}{\rho \omega_2} \right| < \frac{1}{4}.$$

Then,

$$\cos^2 \left(\rho x + \frac{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2}{2} \right) + \frac{O(1)}{\rho \omega_1} + \frac{O(1)}{\rho \omega_2} \geq \frac{1}{4}$$

and

$$\int_{-\frac{\pi}{4} + k\pi}^{\frac{\pi}{4} + k\pi} |y|^2 dx > \frac{1}{4} \int_{-\frac{\pi}{4} + k\pi}^{\frac{\pi}{4} + k\pi} dx = \frac{\pi}{2}.$$

Consequently $\int_0^\infty |y|^2 dx = \infty$, and so we proved the following theorem.

Theorem 2.1. The integro-differential operator L_θ has no eigen-values on the positive semi-axis $\rho > 0$.

Let $\rho_2 = \text{Im } \rho > 0$, then for rather large x

$$|c_1 y|^2 = |c_1|^2 e^{-2\rho_2 x} + \frac{O(1)}{\rho \omega_1}; \quad |c_2 y|^2 = |c_2|^2 e^{2\rho_2 x} + \frac{O(1)}{\rho \omega_2}.$$

Hence it is clear that $c_1 y_1(x) \in \bar{L}^2(R^+)$ for any c_1 and $c_2 y_2(x) \in \bar{L}^2(R^+)$ for any c_2 .

Since $y(x, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^2 c_i y_i(x, \rho)$, then $y(x, \rho)$ can be an eigen-function of the integro-differential operator

L_θ only if $y(x, \rho) \in L^2(R^+)$, i.e. when $c_2 = 0$, $y(x, \rho) = c_1 y_1(x; \rho)$ is an eigen-function of the integro-differential operator L_θ if $y(x, \rho) = c_1 y_1(x; \rho) \in D_\theta$, i.e. $c_1 [y_1'(0, \rho) - \theta y_1(0, \rho)] = 0$ for any $c_1 \neq 0$.

Consequently

$$F_1(\rho) = y'(0, \rho) - \theta y_1(0, \rho) = 0 \quad (2.5)$$

By virtue of theorem 1.1 as was shown in the first part of the paper, $F_1(\rho)$ is an analytic function regular in the upper half-plane, therefore, the solution ρ or of the equation (2.5) form a finite or denumerable set.

The asymptotic formulas

$$y_1(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[1 + \frac{1}{\rho\omega_1} \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) \right],$$

$$\frac{dy_1(x, \rho)}{dx} = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[\rho\omega_1 + O\left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) \right],$$

it follows that

$$F_1(\rho) = y_1'(0, \rho) - \theta y_1(0, \rho) = \rho\omega_1 \left\{ 1 + \left(O \frac{1}{\rho} \right) - \theta \left[1 + \frac{1}{\rho\omega_1} O\left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) \right] \right\} =$$

$$= \rho\omega_1 \left[1 + O\left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) - \frac{\theta}{\rho\omega_1} - O\left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) \right] = \rho\omega_1 \left[1 + O\left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) - \frac{\theta}{\rho\omega_1} - \theta O\left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) \right] \neq 0 \text{ for } |\rho|$$

for rather large $|\rho|$.

So, we proved

Theorem 2.2. The eigen-values of the integro-differential operator L_θ form a bounded finite or denumerable set whose limit point can be located only on the positive semi-axis $\lambda \geq 0$.

We can amplify this theorem if the following condition is fulfilled:

$$|P(x)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, x, \rho)| ds \right] \leq ce^{-2\varepsilon_0 x}, \varepsilon_0 > 0 \quad (2.6)$$

In this case, as was shown in the perilous paper

$$\Phi(\rho) = y'(0, \rho) - \theta y_1(0, \rho)$$

and by virtue of theorem 1.5 is an analytic function in the real line in the plane ρ .

Therefore, the zeros of the function $\Phi(\rho)$ can not have limit points on the real line, axis but as they form a bounded set that does not have other limit points, then these zeros are finite by many. So, we proved the following theorem.

Theorem 2.3. The eigen-values of the integro-differential operator L_θ subject to the condition (2.6) can form only a finite set.

Above we have seen (theorem 2.1) that here are no non-zero eigen-values of the integro-differential operator L_θ on the real axis

We prove the following theorem.

Theorem 2.4. The point $\lambda = 0$ is not an eigen-value of the integro-differential operator L_θ if the condition (2.6) is fulfilled.

Proof. For $\rho = 0$, the integro-differential equation (2.1) and condition (2.3) have the form:

$$y''(x) + p(x)y'(x) + \int_0^\infty k(x, s)y'(s)ds = 0, \quad (2.7)$$

$$k(x, s) = p(s)k^*(x, s), \quad (2.8)$$

respectively, where $k(x, s, 0) = k(x, s)$ and $k^*(x, s, 0) = k^*(x, s)$.

To prove theorem 2.4, it suffices to show that the integro-differential equation (2.1) has no solutions belonging to $L^2(R^+)$.

Let us consider the integro-differential equation

$$y_k(x) = x^{k-1} + \int_x^\infty \left[(\tau - x)p(\tau)y_l'(\tau) + \int_0^\infty (s - x)k(\tau, s)y_k'(s) \right] d\tau, k = 1, 2. \tag{2.9}$$

Considering condition (2.8), we obtain:

$$y_k(x) = x^{k-1} + \int_x^\infty (\tau - x)p(\tau)y_l'(\tau) + \int_x^\infty \int_0^\infty (s - x)p(s)k^*(\tau, s)y_k'(s)dsd\tau, k = 1, 2. \tag{2.10}$$

Show that each of these equations has solutions that as $x \rightarrow \infty$ have the following asymptotics

$$y_1(x) = 1 + o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0x}), \quad y_1'(x) = o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0x}), \tag{2.11}$$

$$y_2(x) = x + o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0x}), \quad y_2'(x) = 1 + o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0x}), \tag{2.12}$$

We carry out the proof for $y_1(x)$ we write the solution of the integro-differential equation (2.1) for $k = 1$ in the form of the Neumann series

$$y_1(x) = 1 + H1 + H^21 + \dots \tag{2.13}$$

where

$$Hy_1 = \int_x^\infty (\tau - x)p(\tau)y_1'(\tau)d\tau + \int_x^\infty \int_0^\infty (s - x)p(s)k^*(\tau, s)y_1'(s)dsd\tau.$$

For $\tau > x \geq 0, \tau - x = t \geq 0, x + t = \tau \geq 0$.

Therefore ,

$$\begin{aligned} |H1| &\leq \int_0^\infty \left[t|p(x+t)| + \int_0^\infty t|p(x+t)||k^*(s, x+t)|ds \right] d\tau = \\ &= \int_0^\infty t|p(x+t)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, x+t)|ds \right] dt \leq \\ &\leq c \int_0^\infty te^{-2\varepsilon_0(x+t)} dt = \frac{ce^{-2\varepsilon_0x}}{(2\varepsilon_0)^2}; \end{aligned}$$

by the induction

$$\begin{aligned} |H^21| &\leq \int_x^\infty (\tau - x)p(\tau) \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, t)|ds \right] |H1|d\tau \leq \\ &\leq \frac{c}{(2\varepsilon_0)^2} \int_0^\infty te^{-4\varepsilon_0(x+t)} dt = \frac{ce^{-4\varepsilon_0x}}{2(2 \cdot 4)\varepsilon_0^4}; \\ |H^n1| &\leq \frac{ce^{-2n\varepsilon_0x}}{2(2n)!!\varepsilon_0^{n+2}} \quad \text{for } (2n)!! = 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \cdot 8 \dots 2k. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the series (2.13) converges uniformly for $x \geq 0$, moreover, $|y_1(x)| \leq A_2$ for $x \in R^+$.

We now estimate the integral term in (2.10) for $k = 1$

$$|Hy_1| \leq A_2|H1| \leq \frac{A_2ce^{-2\varepsilon_0x}}{(2\varepsilon_0)^2} \rightarrow o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0x}) \quad \text{as } x \rightarrow \infty.$$

Thereby, for $y_1(x)$ we proved the relation.

$$y_1(x) = 1 + o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0x})$$

Differentiating both sides of (2.10) for $k = 1$, we obtain

$$y_1(x) = -\int_x^\infty \rho(\tau) \left[1 + \int_0^\infty k^*(s, \tau) ds \right] y_1'(\tau) d\tau.$$

The estimates similar to perilous ones, show that this integral is $o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x})$.
Consequently,

$$y_1'(x) = o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x}).$$

It is clear that $y_1(x)$ will also be the solution of the integro-differential equation (2.7) for $x \in \mathbb{R}^+$.

Further, $y_1(x) \in \bar{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$.

We carry out the same construction for $y_2(x)$. Obviously, $y_2(x) \in \bar{L}^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$.

It is seen from the asymptotics that $y_1(x)$, $y_2(x)$ of the integro-differential equation (2.7) for $\rho = 0$ is

their linear combination: $y(x) = \sum_{i=1}^2 c_i y_i(x)$.

It follows from asymptotic formulas (2.11), (2.12) that no such linear combination other than identical zero belongs to $L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$. The theorem is proved.

We showed that if

$$\int_0^\infty |\rho(\tau)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty k^*(s, \tau) ds \right] d\tau < B < \infty.$$

the eigen-values of the integro-differential operator L_θ from a bounded set (Theorem 2.2) and the Neumann series $B < r$ converges uniformly.

We now find the estimation of the radius of the circle in the complex ρ plane ($\lambda = \rho^2$) outside of which knowing there are no eigen-values of the integro-differential operator L_θ .

Let for simplicity $\theta = \infty$. Then the condition (2.2) takes the form $y(0) = 0$. Choose $r > B$ from the

condition $\frac{B}{r} \leq \frac{1}{4}$.

Then

$$|H^n 1| \leq \left(\frac{B}{r}\right)^n \leq \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^n \quad \text{and} \quad |z(x, \rho)| \geq 1 - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^n \geq \frac{3}{2}$$

for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^+$.

Then from $y_1(x, \rho) = e^{\rho \omega_1 x} z(x, \rho)$ it follows that

$$y_1(x, \rho) = |z(0, \rho)| \geq \frac{2}{3}$$

However the eigen-values of the-integro-differential operator L_θ may be found only among the zeros $y_1(0, \rho) = 0$, and this is impossible.

Consequently, outside a circle of radius

$$r = 4 \int_0^\infty |\rho(\tau)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty k^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right] d\tau$$

there are no eigen-values of the integro-differential operator L_θ .

We now find the explicit expression for the kernel of the resolvent

$$R_\lambda = (L_\theta - \lambda E)^{-1}.$$

Let $\lambda = \rho^2, \rho_2 = \text{Im } \rho > 0$ do not belong to the spectrum of the integro-differential operator L_θ .

We solve the following integro-differential equation

$$-y''(x) - \rho^2 y(x) = f(x) - p(x)y'(x) - \int_0^\infty k^*(x, s, \rho)y'(s)ds \tag{2.14}$$

where $f(x) \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$.

By the method of variation of arbitrary constants, we find

$$y(x, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^2 c_i y_i(x, \rho) + \sum_{i=1}^2 (-1) \frac{y_i(x, \rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} \int_0^\infty y_{3-i}(\tau, \rho) [f(\tau) - p(\tau)y'(\tau, \rho) - \int_0^\infty k(\tau, s, \rho)y'(s, \rho)ds]d\tau. \tag{2.15}$$

We find c_1 and c_2 .

Assume that the domain of definition of the resolvent R_λ contains the functions $f(x)$ that are equal to zero outside arbitrary finite interval $[0, a]$, below we will see that this circumstance does not really take place. We denote the totality of all such functions $f(x)$ by D' . If $f(x) \in D'$, then for $x > a$

$$y(x, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^2 c_i y_i(x, \rho) + \sum_{i=1}^2 (-1) \frac{y_i(x, \rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} \int_0^a y_{3-i}(\tau, \rho) [f(\tau) - p(\tau)y'(\tau, \rho) - \int_0^\infty k(\tau, s, \rho)y'(s, \rho)ds]d\tau. \tag{2.16}$$

but $y(x, \rho) \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$ while $c_2 y_2(x) \notin L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$. therefore the equality (2.16) is possible under the condition

$$c_2 = -\frac{1}{2\rho\omega_1} \int_0^\infty y_1(\tau, \rho) [f(\tau) - p(\tau)y'(\tau, \rho) - \int_0^\infty k(\tau, s, \rho)y'(s, \rho)ds]d\tau.$$

We find c_1 from the boundary condition (2.2).

Since

$$y(0, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^2 c_i y_i(0, \rho) \text{ and } y'(0, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^2 c_i y_i'(0, \rho), \text{ then}$$

$$y'(0, \rho) - \theta y(0, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^2 c_i F_i(\rho) = 0, \text{ where } F_i(\rho) = y_i'(0, \rho) - \theta y_i(0, \rho), \quad i = 1, 2.$$

Due to the choice of the point $\lambda, F_1(\rho) \neq 0$, therefore,

$$c_1 = -\frac{F_2(\rho)}{F_1(\rho)} c_2 = \frac{F(\rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} \int_0^\infty y_1(\tau, \rho) [f(\tau) - p(\tau)y'(\tau, \rho) - \int_0^\infty k(\tau, s, \rho)y'(s, \rho)ds]d\tau \text{ where } F(\rho) = \frac{F_2(\rho)}{F_1(\rho)}.$$

Substituting the found values of c_1 and c_2 to (2.16), and considering condition (2.3), we obtain

$$y(x, \rho) = \int_0^\infty M(x, \tau, \rho)d\tau + \int_0^\infty N(x, \tau, \rho)y(\tau, \rho)d\tau \tag{2.17}$$

where

$$M(x, \tau, \rho) = \begin{cases} \frac{F(\rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} e^{\rho\omega_1(x+\tau)} - \frac{e^{\rho\omega_1(x-\tau)}}{2\rho\omega_1} & \text{as } \tau < x, \\ \frac{F(\rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} e^{\rho\omega_1(x+\tau)} - \frac{e^{\rho\omega_1(\tau-x)}}{2\rho\omega_1} & \text{as } \tau > x, \end{cases} \quad (2.18)$$

$$N(x, \tau, \rho) = \begin{cases} \frac{P(\tau)}{2\rho\omega_1} \left\{ -F(\rho)e^{\rho\omega_1(x+\tau)} + e^{\rho\omega_1(x-\tau)} \left[1 + \int_0^\infty (1-F(\rho))e^{2\rho\omega_1 s} \right] \times \right. \\ \left. \times k^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right\} & \text{as } \tau < x, \\ \frac{P(\tau)}{2\rho\omega_1} \left\{ -F(\rho)e^{\rho\omega_1(x+\tau)} + e^{\rho\omega_1(x-\tau)} \left[1 + \int_0^\infty (1-F(\rho))e^{2\rho\omega_1 x} \times \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \times k^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right] \right\} & \text{as } \tau > x, \end{cases} \quad (2.19)$$

Since $\lambda = \rho^2$, $\text{Im } \rho > 0$ does not belong to the spectrum of the integro-differential operator L_θ , the homogeneous equation (2.14) and consequently the homogeneous equation (2.17) have only a trivial solution.

Therefore, (2.17) and consequently, the equation (2.14) and are solvable for any $f(x) \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$.

$$y(x, \rho) = R_\lambda f = \int_0^\infty \left[M(x, \tau, \rho) + \int_0^\infty \Gamma(x, \tau, \rho) M(t, \tau, \rho) dt \right] f(\tau) d\tau. \quad (2.20)$$

i.e. on the functions $f(x) \in D'$ the resolvent is an integral operator with the kernel

$$T_0(x, \tau, \rho) = M(x, \tau, \rho) + \int_0^\infty \Gamma(x, \tau, \rho) M(t, \tau, \rho) dt. \quad (2.21)$$

$\Gamma(x, \tau, \rho)$ is a resolvent kernel for the kernel $N(x, t, \rho)$.

Prove that this kernel gives an integral operator bounded and determined on the space $L_2(\mathbb{R}^+)$ for all ρ not belonging to the spectrum.

Denote by

$$Q_1(x, \tau, \rho) = \frac{F(\rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} e^{\rho\omega_1(x+\tau)},$$

$$Q_2(x, \tau, \rho) = -\frac{1}{2\rho\omega_1} \begin{cases} e^{\rho\omega_1(x-\tau)}, & \text{for } \tau < x, \\ e^{\rho\omega_1(\tau-x)}, & \text{for } \tau > x, \end{cases}$$

$$\Phi_1(x, \tau, \rho) = -\frac{F(\rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} P(\tau) e^{\rho\omega_1(x+\tau)},$$

$$\Phi_2(x, \tau, \rho) = \begin{cases} \frac{e^{\rho\omega_1(x-\tau)} P(\tau)}{2\rho\omega_1} \left\{ 1 + \int_0^\infty [1 - F(\rho)e^{2\rho\omega_1 s}] k^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right\} & \text{as } \tau < x, \\ \frac{e^{\rho\omega_1(\tau-x)} P(\tau)}{2\rho\omega_1} \left\{ 1 + \int_0^\infty [1 - F(\rho)e^{2\rho\omega_1 x}] k^*(x, s, \rho) ds \right\} & \text{as } \tau > x, \end{cases}$$

Then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} M(x, \tau, \rho) &= Q_1(x, \tau, \rho) + Q_2(x, \tau, \rho), \\ N(x, \tau, \rho) &= \Phi_1(x, \tau, \rho) + \Phi_2(x, \tau, \rho). \end{aligned}$$

It follows from the asymptotic formulas for

$$y_1(x) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[1 + \frac{O(1)}{\rho\omega_1} \right] \text{ as } x \rightarrow \infty \tag{2.22}$$

that $Q_1(x, \tau, \rho)$ is Hilbert-Schmidt kernel, and

$$|Q_1(x, \tau, \rho)| \leq ce^{-\rho_2(x+\tau)}.$$

Therefore, it determines not only a bounded but also completely continuous operator.

It what follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Phi_1\|^2 &\leq \int_0^\infty \left| \int_0^\infty -\frac{F(\rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} e^{\rho\omega_1(x+\tau)} p(\tau) d\tau \right|^2 dx \leq \\ &\leq \int_0^\infty \left[\int_0^\infty \frac{|F(\rho)|}{2|\rho|} e^{-\rho_2(x+\tau)} |p(\tau)| d\tau \right]^2 dx \leq \\ &\leq \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \frac{|F^2(\rho)|}{4|\rho|^2} e^{-2\rho_2(x+\tau)} d\tau dx \int_0^\infty |p(\tau)|^2 d\tau = \frac{|F^2(\rho)|}{4|\rho|^2 \rho_2^2} \|p\|^2. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\|\Phi_1\| \leq \frac{|F(\rho)|}{2\rho_2|\rho|} \|p\|.$

Therefore, it suffices to prove our statement for $Q_2(x, \tau, \rho)$ and $\Phi_2(x, \tau, \rho)$.

For the special case $p(x) \equiv 0, \theta = 0$, L_θ is a positive- definite self-adjoint operator, therefore its spectrum is located o the positive semi-axis. If λ is not located on the positive semi-axis, its resolvent R_λ is a bounded operator determined in the space $L_2(R^+)$ and the norm of the resolvent does not exceed $\frac{1}{d}$, where d is the distance of the point λ to the positive semi-axis.

Consequently, in this special case, the kernel of the resolvent gives a bounded integral operator determined in the space $L_2(R^+)$, and the norm of this operator does not exceed

$$\frac{1}{d} + \|Q_1\| \leq \frac{1}{d} + \frac{|F(\rho)|}{4\rho_2|\rho|}.$$

For this special case $y_k(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_k x}, k = 1, 2, F_k(\rho) = y_k'(0, \rho), k = 1, 2.$

Therefore, $F(\rho) = 1$ and $Q_1(x, \tau, \rho) = -\frac{e^{\rho\omega_1(x+\tau)}}{2\rho\omega_1};$

$$\|Q_1(x, \tau, \rho)\|^2 \leq \int_0^\infty \left| \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{\rho\omega_1(x+\tau)}}{2\rho\omega_1} d\tau \right|^2 dx = \left(\frac{1}{4\rho_2|\rho|} \right)^2;$$

$$\|Q_1(x, \tau, \rho)\| \leq \frac{1}{4\rho_2|\rho|}$$

Therefore,

$$\|Q_2\| \leq \frac{1}{d} + \frac{1}{4\rho_2|\rho|}.$$

This means that the following inequality is fulfilled for any function $f(x) \in L^2(R^+)$

$$\int_0^\infty \left| \int_0^\infty Q_2(x, \tau, \rho) f(\tau) d\tau \right|^2 dx \leq \left(\frac{1}{d} + \frac{1}{4\rho_2|\rho|} \right)^2 \|f\|^2 \quad (2.24)$$

Let $\rho = \rho_2\omega_1, \rho_2 > 0$, consequently, $\lambda = -\rho_2^2$. Then

$$Q_2(x, \tau, \rho) = \frac{1}{2\rho_2} \begin{cases} e^{-\rho_2(x-\tau)} & \text{as } \tau < x, \\ e^{-\rho_2(x-\tau)} & \text{as } \tau > x, \end{cases} \quad (2.25)$$

Substituting (2.25), (2.26) in (2.4), we obtain the inequality

$$\frac{1}{4\rho_2^2} \int_0^\infty \left| \int_0^x \frac{1}{2\rho_2} e^{-\rho_2(x-\tau)} f(\tau) d\tau + \int_x^\infty \frac{1}{2\rho_2} e^{-\rho_2(\tau-x)} f(\tau) d\tau \right|^2 dx \leq \frac{25}{16\rho_2^4} \|f\|^2 \quad (2.26)$$

If $f(x) \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$, then $|f(x)| \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$. Replacing $f(x)$ by $|f(x)|$, in (2.26) we get the inequality

$$\frac{1}{4\rho_2^2} \int_0^\infty \left[e^{-\rho_2 x} \int_0^x e^{\rho_2 \tau} |f(\tau)| d\tau + e^{\rho_2 x} \int_x^\infty e^{-\rho_2 \tau} |f(\tau)| d\tau \right]^2 dx \leq \frac{25}{16\rho_2^4} \|f\|^2 \quad (2.27)$$

We come back to the general case. From the asymptotic formulas for $y_2(x) = e^{\rho\omega_2 x} \left[1 + O\left(\frac{1}{\rho\omega_2}\right) \right]$

for $\rho_2 > 0$ it follows that

$$|y_1(x, \rho)| \leq ce^{-\rho_2 x}, \quad |y_2(x, \rho)| \leq ce^{\rho_2 x}. \quad (2.28)$$

Using the definition $Q_2(x, \tau, \rho)$ and the inequalities (2.27), (2.28), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^\infty \left| \int_0^\infty Q_2(x, \tau, \rho) f(\tau) d\tau \right|^2 dx \leq \\ & \leq \int_0^\infty \left| -\frac{y_1(x, \rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} \int_0^\infty y_2(\tau, \rho) f(\tau) d\tau - \frac{y_2(x, \rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} \int_x^\infty y_1(\tau, \rho) f(\tau) d\tau \right|^2 dx \leq \\ & \leq \frac{c^2}{4|\rho|^2} \int_0^\infty \left[e^{-\rho_2 x} \int_0^x e^{\rho_2 \tau} |f(\tau)| d\tau + e^{\rho_2 x} \int_x^\infty e^{-\rho_2 \tau} |f(\tau)| d\tau \right]^2 dx \leq \frac{25c^2}{16\rho_2^2|\rho|^2} \|f\|^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{i.e. } \|Q_2\| \leq \frac{5c}{4\rho_2|\rho|}.$$

$$\|M(x, \tau, \rho)\| \leq \|Q_1(x, \tau, \rho)\| + \|Q_2(x, \tau, \rho)\| \leq \frac{l}{\rho_2|\rho|} \text{ where } l = \frac{1+5c}{4}.$$

We now consider $T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho)$.

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^\infty \left| \int_0^\infty T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho) f(\tau) d\tau \right|^2 dx = \\ & = \int_0^\infty \left| \int_0^\infty M(x, \tau, \rho) f(\tau) d\tau + \int_0^\infty \Gamma(x, \tau, \rho) \left[\int_0^\infty M(\tau, t, \rho) f(t) dt \right] \right|^2 dx \leq \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq 2 \int_0^\infty \left| \int_0^\infty T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho) f(\tau) d\tau \right|^2 dx + 2 \int_0^\infty \left| \int_0^\infty \Gamma(x, \tau, \rho) \left[\int_0^\infty M(\tau, t, \rho) f(t) dt \right] d\tau \right|^2 dx \leq \\ &\leq \frac{2l^2 \|f\|^2}{\rho_2^2 |\rho|^2} + 2 \int_0^\infty \left| \int_0^\infty \Gamma(x, \tau, \rho) \left[\int_0^\infty M(\tau, t, \rho) f(t) dt \right] d\tau \right|^2 dx \leq \frac{2l^2 \|f\|^2}{\rho_2^2 |\rho|^2} + \\ &\quad + 2 \int_0^\infty \left[\int_0^\infty |\Gamma(x, \tau, \rho)|^2 d\tau \right] dx \int_0^\infty \left[\int_0^\infty M(\tau, t, \rho) f(t) dt \right]^2 \leq \\ &\leq \frac{2l^2 \|f\|^2}{\rho_2^2 |\rho|^2} + \frac{2l^2 \|f\|^2}{\rho_2^2 |\rho|^2} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty |\Gamma(x, \tau, \rho)|^2 d\tau dx, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} &\left[\int_0^\infty |\Gamma(x, \tau, \rho)| \left| \int_0^\infty M(\tau, t, \rho) f(t) dt \right| d\tau \right]^2 \leq \\ &\leq \int_0^\infty |\Gamma(x, \tau, \rho)|^2 d\tau \int_0^\infty \left| \int_0^\infty M(\tau, t, \rho) f(t) dt \right|^2 d\tau \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\|T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho)\| \leq \frac{\sqrt{2}l}{\rho_2 |\rho|} \sqrt{1 + \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty |\Gamma(x, \tau, \rho)|^2 dx d\tau}.$$

Using

$$\Gamma(x, \tau, \rho) = \sum_{n=1}^\infty N_n(x, \tau, \rho), \tag{2.29}$$

$$N_1(x, \tau, \rho) = N(x, \tau, \rho) \text{ and } N_n(x, \tau, \rho) = \int_0^\infty N_1(x, \tau_1, \rho) N_{n-1}(\tau_1, \tau, \rho) d\tau_1,$$

we show that if $|\rho|$ is rather large, i.e.

$$|\rho| \left[1 + O\left(\frac{1}{|\rho|^2}\right) \right] > \frac{B}{q}, \text{ then } \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty |\Gamma(x, \tau, \rho)|^2 dx d\tau < \infty.$$

As first we show that the series (2.28) converges uniformly if $|\rho| \left[1 + O\left(\frac{1}{|\rho|^2}\right) \right] > \frac{B}{q}$

Indeed, for $\tau < x$, $\text{Im } \rho > 0$ we have $e^{-\rho_2(x-\tau)} \leq 1$, $e^{-2\rho_2 s} \leq 1$ and for $\tau > x$, $\text{Im } \rho = \rho_2 > 0$, we have $e^{-\rho_2(x-\tau)} \leq 1$, $e^{-2\rho_2 x} \leq 1$; and also for $\tau > x$ and $\tau < x$, $e^{-2\rho_2(x+\tau)} \leq 1$.

Hence, from (2.19) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |N_1(x, \tau, \rho)| &\leq \frac{|p(\tau)| [|F(\rho)| + 1]}{2|\rho|} \left[1 + \int_0^\infty k^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right]; \\ |N_2(x, \tau, \rho)| &\leq \int_0^\infty |N_1(x, \tau, \rho)| |N_1(\tau_1, \tau, \rho)| d\tau \leq \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \frac{[|F(\rho)|+1]}{2|\rho|} |p(\tau)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \int_0^\infty \frac{[|F(\rho)|+1]}{2|\rho|} |p(\tau_1)| \right] \times$$

$$\times \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] d\tau_1 \leq \frac{[|F(\rho)|+1]^2}{(2|\rho|)^2} B |p(\tau)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right],$$

by the induction

$$|N_n(x, \tau, \rho)| \leq \frac{[|F(\rho)|+1]^n}{(2|\rho|)^n} B^{n-1} |p(\tau)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right].$$

Therefore,

$$|\Gamma(x, \tau, \rho)| \leq \sum_{n=1}^\infty \left(\frac{|F(\rho)|+1}{2|\rho|} \right)^n B^{n-1} |p(\tau)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] =$$

$$= \frac{|F(\rho)|+1}{2|\rho|} |p(\tau)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] \sum_{n=1}^\infty \left(\frac{|F(\rho)|+1}{2|\rho|} B \right)^{n-1}.$$

The series $\sum_{n=1}^\infty \left(\frac{|F(\rho)|+1}{2|\rho|} B \right)^{n-1}$ converges if $\frac{|F(\rho)|+1}{2|\rho|} B < q < 1$, i.e. $\frac{|\rho|}{|F(\rho)|+1} < \frac{B}{2q}$

or $|\rho| \left[1 + O\left(\frac{1}{|\rho|^2}\right) \right] > \frac{B}{q}$ and its sum equals $\frac{2|\rho|}{2|\rho| - [|F(\rho)|+1] B}$.

Then the series (2.29) converges uniformly for all $|\rho|$ satisfying $|\rho| \left[1 + O\left(\frac{1}{|\rho|^2}\right) \right] > \frac{B}{q}$ in the domain

$\text{Im } \rho = \rho_2 > 0$.

Then

$$\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty |\Gamma(x, \tau, \rho)|^2 dx d\tau \leq$$

$$\leq \left(\int_0^\infty \frac{|F(\rho)|+1}{2|\rho|} |p(\tau)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \frac{2|\rho|}{2|\rho| - (|F(\rho)|+1)B} d\tau \right]^2 \right) =$$

$$= \left(\frac{|F(\rho)|+1}{2|\rho| - (|F(\rho)|+1)B} \right)^2.$$

So, for any function $f(x) \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$ the formula (2.20) determines such functions $y(x) \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$ that $y(x) \in D(L_\theta)$ and $L_\theta y - \lambda y = f$.

Consequently, the domain of change of $L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$ is the whole space and this resolvent coincides with the integral operator with the kernel $T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho)$.

Thus, we proved the following theorem.

Theorem 2.5. For λ that do not belong to the spectrum, the resolvent of the itegro-differential operator L_θ is a bounded integral operator with the kernel $T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho)$, satisfying the conditions

$$\int_0^{\infty} |T_{\theta}(x, \tau, \rho)|^2 dx < \infty, \int_0^{\infty} |T_{\theta}(x, \tau, \rho)|^2 d\tau < \infty.$$

The last statement follows from the formulas (2.21),(2.22) and asymptotic properties of $y_1(x, \rho), y_2(x, \rho)$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$.

The following corollary follows from the boundedness of the integro-differential operator L_{θ} .

Corollary 2.1. The integro-differential operator L_{θ} closed.

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